

Partition Coefficient of Iodine between Binary Organic Liquid Mixture and Water at 30°

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The partition coefficient of iodine between binary organic liquid mixture (viz. benzene-chloroform benzene-carbon tetrachloride and benzene-toluene) and water were determined at 30°. New equations have been formulated to correlate the variation of partition coefficient with the composition internal pressure and dielectric constant of the liquid mixtures.

SEVERAL works have been done in determining the partition coefficient of a solute between two immiscible organic liquids and their extensive uses in extraction chemistry have been reported. However, based on the principles of extraction of a solute from a solvent, it is of interest to study the partition coefficient of a solute between liquid mixtures and pure liquid which are immiscible. Also it is worthwhile to study the variation of partition coefficient with the physical and chemical properties of the liquid mixtures.

The present study has been undertaken to see whether there is any change in the partition coefficient of iodine when mixtures of organic liquids are used instead of pure liquids and whether such changes can be related to physical properties such as dielectric constant and internal pressure of the liquid mixture. The systems employed are the mixtures benzene(1)-chloroform(2), benzene(1)-carbon tetrachloride(2) and benzene(1)-toluene(2).

Experimental

All the chemicals used were of AnalaR grade. The organic liquids were purified by the reported procedure¹. Double-distilled water was used.

Mixtures of different known compositions of the two liquids under study were prepared as and when required on weight basis. The mixtures were kept in a thermostat at 30°. Partition coefficients of iodine between these liquid mixtures and water were determined by the usual procedure². Density of the liquid mixtures was determined using specific gravity bottle with an accuracy of $\pm 0.00001 \text{ g ml}^{-1}$ and viscosity using an Ostwald's Viscometer with an accuracy of ± 0.00001 centipoise. Ultrasonic velocities were measured using an ultrasonic interferometer, capable of producing ultrasonic waves of the order of 3 MHz with an accuracy $\pm 0.01 \text{ m s}^{-1}$. The dielectric constant was determined using a DM-01 dipolmeter with a precision of 0.002D. All the measurements were done at 30° with the use of circulating water through the instruments from a thermostat which was set initially at 30° ($\pm 0.1^\circ$).

Results and Discussion

All the experimental data are presented in Table 1. Fig. 1 shows the variation of partition coefficient of iodine with the mole fraction of the liquid(1). In all the three systems, the partition coefficient vary with the composition of the liquid

TABLE 1

Mole frac- tion of benzene X_1	Temp = 30° Density (ρ) g ml^{-1}	Viscosity (η) poise	Ultrasonic velocity (U) m s^{-1}	Internal pressure (π) atm		Concn. of iodine in organic layer (C) ¹ gmol dm^{-3}	Pattern coefficient (K)		Dielectric constant (ϵ)	
				Exp	Calcd. eqn (4)		Exp	Calcd. eqn (2)		
Benzene (1)-Chloroform (2) system										
0 000 00	1 467 90	0 005 991 5	967 8	3 998 91	—	0 056 01	125.0	—	4 650	
0 099 76	1 370 29	0 005 923 9	998 4	3 895.63	3 902 08	0.052 20	130 0	135.7	4 125	
0 200 11	1 286 30	0 005 871 4	1 024 2	3 831 17	3 827 29	0.050 93	140 1	148.2	3 755	
0 300 25	1 213 40	0 005 831 6	1 058 2	3 776 01	3 773.46	0.044 57	162 0	162 7	3 470	
0 399 28	1 144 80	0.005 804 7	1 087 2	3 741.84	3 740 41	0 049 65	182 6	179 2	3 215	
0 500 50	1 087 17	0.005 774 9	1 121.2	3 726 36	3 726.64	0 053 47	204 3	198 7	3.005	
0 600 29	1.033 40	0 005 767 6	1 151.0	3 734 71	3 732.64	0.050 93	228 9	221.1	2.830	
0 700 49	0.985 27	0 005 743 5	1 179 0	3 758 07	3 758 32	0 059 84	252.9	247 3	2 660	
0 800 49	0 942 98	0.005 746 3	1 213 2	3 799 82	3 803.88	0 056 01	281 7	277 8	2 520	
0 900 11	0 904 55	0 005 751 3	1 244.4	3 865 12	3 870 14	0 052 20	309 4	313 6	2.390	
1 000 00	0 868 19	0 005 775 9	1 272.9	3 958.19	—	0 073 16	366 0	—	2 265	

(Table 1 contd.)

Benzene(1)-Carbon tetrachloride(2) system									
0.000 00	1.575 10	0.008 892 0	913.8	3 908.96	—	0.064 88	85	—	2.225
0.099 50	1.453 16	0.008 304 0	950.8	3 722.93	3 726.09	0.073 17	120	109.7	2.233
0.200 18	1.346 94	0.007 913 8	988.0	3 604.83	3 589.62	0.067 65	152	138.6	2.240
0.300 70	1.258 23	0.007 450 5	1 025.0	3 504.85	3 496.62	0.057 29	184	170.6	2.245
0.406 24	1.178 41	0.007 045 6	1 059.0	3 455.74	3 441.88	0.063 51	215	207.0	2.250
0.500 12	1.115 01	0.006 756 3	1 095.0	3 438.05	3 429.35	0.065 59	246	239.9	2.255
0.600 44	1.052 25	0.006 484 4	1 130.0	3 452.51	3 452.72	0.070 41	272	274.4	2.257
0.696 95	0.997 48	0.006 262 0	1 167.0	3 494.10	3 511.55	0.077 31	298	304.9	2.260
0.800 37	0.949 45	0.006 124 3	1 197.0	3 628.21	3 616.94	0.058 67	322	332.9	2.262
0.899 22	0.905 89	0.005 906 0	1 237.8	3 744.09	3 768.46	0.067 65	345	353.2	2.264
1.000 00	0.863 19	0.005 776 7	1 272.9	3 959.19	—	0.073 16	366	—	2.265

Benzene(1)-Toluene(2) system									
0.000 00	0.857 69	0.005 433 6	1 295.4	3 112.39	—	0.069 40	501	—	2.380
0.099 50	0.857 85	0.005 454 4	1 288.0	3 183.93	3 181.76	0.065 86	480	482.6	2.365
0.200 11	0.858 02	0.005 475 2	1 282.8	3 255.81	3 253.64	0.067 28	466	465.5	2.352
0.299 91	0.858 57	0.005 498 5	1 279.0	3 329.71	3 328.78	0.071 53	450	449.5	2.340
0.406 34	0.859 26	0.005 532 5	1 275.9	3 413.35	3 412.57	0.075 07	438	434.0	2.330
0.500 16	0.860 37	0.005 559 5	1 273.5	3 489.83	3 489.70	0.072 90	422	421.5	2.315
0.599 20	0.861 20	0.005 594 5	1 272.0	3 573.32	3 575.04	0.063 74	410	409.0	2.305
0.700 37	0.862 25	0.005 631 1	1 271.0	3 661.25	3 665.18	0.063 03	400	397.0	2.295
0.799 84	0.863 90	0.005 671 7	1 270.5	3 753.99	3 758.28	0.064 45	386	386.6	2.282
0.900 40	0.865 01	0.005 724 7	1 270.8	3 855.15	3 856.49	0.063 70	376	377.0	2.272
1.000 00	0.868 19	0.005 779 7	1 272.9	3 958.19	—	0.073 16	366	—	2.265

Fig. 1. Variation of partition coefficient of iodine with the composition of the liquid mixture: (O) benzene(1)-chloroform(2), (□) benzene(1)-carbon tetrachloride(2), (Δ) benzene(1)-toluene(2).

mixture and the variation can be represented by equation(1),

$$\log K = \log K_2 + \alpha X_1 + \beta X_1^2 \quad (1)$$

This equation can be modified as

$$\log K = X_2 \log K_2 + X_1 \log K_1 - \beta X_1 X_2 \quad (2)$$

where, K is the partition coefficient of iodine between liquid mixtures and water, K_1 and K_2 are the partition coefficient of iodine using liquid(1) and liquid(2) separately with water, X_1 and X_2 the mole fractions of liquid(1) and liquid(2) in the mixture, and α and β are constants. The constant appearing in equation (2) was calculated through the least-square method. The absolute deviation of the observed partition coefficient values from those calculated by using equation (2) shows a good concordance of the data.

Internal pressure of the liquid mixtures were computed using the equation³,

$$\pi = bRT \left[\frac{K\eta}{U} \right]^{\frac{1}{2}} \frac{\rho^{2/3}}{M^{7/6}} \quad (3)$$

where, π is the internal pressure, b the packing factor which is equal to 2 for cubic packing, T the temperature in absolute scale, K a constant having the value 4.28×10^9 , η the viscosity of the liquid mixture, U the ultrasonic velocity of the liquid mixture, ρ the density of the liquid mixture, and M the average molecular weight of the liquid mixture.

$$M = (X_1 M_1 + X_2 M_2)$$

where, M_1 and M_2 are the molecular weights of liquid(1) and liquid(2), and X_1 and X_2 their corresponding mole fractions.

Fig. 2 shows the variation of internal pressure of the liquid mixtures with the composition. The variation is found to follow an equation similar to equation (2),

$$\log \pi = X_1 \log \pi_1 + X_2 \log \pi_2 - B X_1 X_2 \quad (4)$$

Fig. 2 Variation of internal pressure with the composition of the liquid mixture: (O) benzene(1)-chloroform(2), (□) benzene(1)-carbon tetrachloride(2), (Δ) benzene(1)-toluene(2)

where, π is the internal pressure of the liquid mixture, π_1 and π_2 are the internal pressure of the liquid(1) and liquid(2), and X_1 and X_2 their mole fractions. The constant B appearing in equation (4) was calculated through the least-square method. The absolute deviation of the observed data from the

calculated data using equation (4) shows a good concordance of the data.

From Table 2 it is well-understood that the magnitude of β and B are proportional to each other. This reveals that the values of β or B is a measure of deviation from ideal behaviour.

The variation of partition coefficient with dielectric constant is correlated through equation (5),

$$K = a \epsilon^b \quad (5)$$

where, K is the partition coefficient, ϵ the dielectric constant of the ligand or liquid mixture, and a and b are constants. In all the three systems the plots of $\ln K$ vs $\ln \epsilon$ is a straight line (figures not shown). The values of correlation coefficient (r) which are greater than 0.98 for all the three systems show a good correlation.

In the case of benzene-chloroform system the partition coefficient decreases with increasing dielectric constant while in the other two systems, the partition coefficient increases with increasing dielectric constant. This observation can be explained in terms of the following two factors. (i) Physical interaction: Non-polar solute such as iodine is more soluble in a non-polar solvent such as benzene, toluene, etc., than in a polar solvent such as water, chloroform, etc. As a result, in the benzene-chloroform system, as the concentration of chloroform increases the polarity of the liquid mixture increases, the solubility of iodine decreases and hence the partition coefficient decreases with increasing concentration of chloroform. (ii) Lewis acid-base type of interaction or chemical interaction: In the case of benzene-carbon tetrachloride and benzene-toluene systems, the partition coefficient increases with increasing dielectric constant. This variation can not be explained on the basis polarity of the liquid mixture alone.

Fair Brother⁴ showed the presence of Lewis acid-base type of interaction between iodine and benzene. Benzene is basic due to its π -electrons, its solubility in sulphuric acid and its reactions with AlCl_3 , BF_3 , etc. Iodine is acidic due to its reactions with I^- ,

In the case of benzene-carbon tetrachloride system, the Lewis acid-base interaction overcomes the interaction based on polarity of the solvent and solute. Therefore the solubility of iodine increases with

TABLE 2

System	β From eqn. (2)	% Absolute deviation for eqn (4)	β From eqn. (4)	% Absolute deviation for eqn. (4)	From eqn (6)	
					a	b
Benzene(1)-Chloroform(2)	0 104 6	1.75	0.113 6	0.06	1.17×10^8	-1 544
Benzene(1)-Carbon tetrachloride(2)	-0 534 7	3 05	0 238 3	0.24	$1 73 \times 10^{-17}$	82 611
Benzene(1)-Toluene(2)	0 032 1	0.28	0.010 1	0 04	2 1815	6.270

increasing concentration of benzene, and hence the partition coefficient increases with increasing concentration of benzene though benzene has a higher dielectric constant than carbon tetrachloride.

In the case of benzene-toluene system, toluene is more basic than benzene due to the increased electron density in the ring by the electron-releasing methyl group. So in this case the partition coefficient increases with increasing concentration of toluene.

References

1. A. WEISSBERGER, "Technique of Organic Chemistry, Organic Solvents", Interscience, New York, 1960, Vol. VII.
2. D. SHOEMAKER and C. GARLAND, "Experiments in Physical Chemistry", McGraw-Hill, New York, 1962, p. 181.
3. C. V. SURYANARAYANA, *J. Acous. India*, 1979, **7**, 131; C. V. SURYANARAYANA and J. KUPPUSAMY, *J. Acous. Soc. India*, 1976, **4**, 75.
4. F. FAIR BROTHER, *Nature (London)*, 1947, **160**, 87; *J. Chem. Soc.*, 1948, 1051.